

ANTIMICROBIAL ACTIVITY OF ETHANOLIC CRUDE EXTRACTS OF MEDICINAL PLANTS AND THEIR CYCLODEXTRIN-ENCAPSULATED FORMS

¹Abdullaeva M.O., ¹Gayibova S.N., ¹Gayibov U.G., ²Amirsaidova D.A., ³Umarova F.T.,
¹Aripov T.F.

¹Institute of Bioorganic Chemistry of the Academy of sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan

²Microbiology Institute of the Academy of sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan

³Institute of Biophysics and biochemistry, NUUz, Tashkent, Uzbekistan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13828185>

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqola *Rhodiola heterodonta* L., *Inula helenium* L., *Ginkgo biloba* L. ekstraktlari va ularning γ - va 2-gidroksipropil- β -siklodextrinlar bilan inkapsulyatsiyalarini ba'zi shartli-patogen mikroorganizmlarga qarshi salohiyatini baholashga qaratilgan. *R. heterodonta*, *I. helenium* va *G. biloba* maksimal mikroblarga qarshi faolligi borligi aniqlandi. Ekstraktlar turli usullar bilan siklodextrinlar bilan kapsulalanganda mikroblarga qarshi faollik *I. helenium*da kamayadi, *R. heterodonta* va *G. biloba*da esa ortadi. Xususan, siklodextrin turining ahamiyati va inkapsulyatsiya jarayoni ham alohida ahamiyatga ega.

Kalit so'zlar: biomoyillik, polifenol, gidrofob, gidrofil, nanotexnologiya, mikroorganizmlar.

Аннотация. Целью данной работы является оценка антимикробиологического потенциала экстрактов *Rhodiola heterodonta* L., *Inula helenium* L., *Ginkgo biloba* L. и их инкапсулированных циклодекстринами форм против некоторых условно-патогенных микроорганизмов. Было показано, что антимикробная активность экстракта *I. helenium* при инкапсулировании снижается, тогда как экстракты *R. heterodonta* и *G. biloba* проявляют повышенную антимикробную активность при инкапсулировании. В частности, особую роль при инкапсулировании играют тип циклодекстрина и метод инкапсулирования.

Ключевые слова: биодоступность, полифенолы, гидрофобность, гидрофильность, нанотехнология, микроорганизм.

Abstract. This article aims to evaluate the potential of *Rhodiola heterodonta* L., *Inula helenium* L., and *Ginkgo biloba* L. extracts and their encapsulation with γ - and 2-hydroxypropyl- β -cyclodextrins against some opportunistic pathogenic microorganisms. We found significant antimicrobial activity in *R. heterodonta*, *I. helenium*, and *G. biloba*. Different methods of encapsulating the extracts with cyclodextrins led to a decrease in antimicrobial activity in *I. helenium*, but an increase in *R. heterodonta* and *G. biloba*. We also observed that the type of cyclodextrin and the encapsulation process play a crucial role.

Keywords: bioavailability, polyphenol, hydrophobic, hydrophilic, nanotechnology, microorganism.

Introduction. Medicinal herbs are considered alternatives to antibiotics due to their broad spectrum of secondary metabolites that inhibit bacterial growth and/or kill bacterial cells. However, many secondary metabolites, such as polyphenols, have low water solubility, leading to inadequate bioavailability and reduced therapeutic effects. Nanotechnology advances, such as liposomes, micelles, nanogels, and dendrimers, have helped unlock the medicinal potential of

dietary polyphenols by making them more bioavailable, lowering side effects, and allowing drugs to be delivered only to the right place. Cyclodextrins (CDs), which are cyclic oligosaccharides, are also promising encapsulating agents. Their special structure, with a hydrophobic cavity inside and a hydrophilic surface outside, makes it easy for different compounds to get inside. Adding gamma-cyclodextrin (γ -CD) to high-calorie kudin tea extract, which is an herbal tea made from the dried leaves of *Radum latifolia* L., was found to raise the levels of PPAR γ , CD36, CYP7A1, CYP3A, and GSTA1 enzymes in the liver that break down xenobiotics. It also caused the liver to gain weight and fat [1]. This study also found that tocotrienol-rich parts of rice bran were more bioavailable and had more physiological activity when they were encapsulated with γ -CD. In the same way, adding γ -CD to Brazilian green propolis extract lowered the levels of hepatic tumor necrosis factor-alpha and Sap mRNA, showing strong anti-inflammatory effects [3]. Grapevine extract encapsulated in hydroxypropyl-beta-cyclodextrin (HP- β -CD) allowed for the recycling of viticultural by-products that were previously limited by instability and low water solubility [4]. A study by Hsu et al. found that combining rhubarb extract with HP- β -CD made rhubarb more water-soluble and bioavailable, which made it more effective against hepatoma cells [5]. Despite numerous studies on the patterns and molecular mechanisms of action, interest in encapsulating plant extracts with cyclodextrins remains high. The antimicrobial effects of cyclodextrin-encapsulated extracts from *Rhodiola heterodonta* L., an endemic Uzbekistan plant, as well as *Inula helenium* L. and *Ginkgo biloba* L. were studied in this study.

Materials and methods. Plant extracts were generously provided by Ltd. BIOTON. The cyclodextrins used were γ -CD and 2-hydroxypropyl- β -cyclodextrin (2-HP- β -CD) from Cyclolab, Hungary. CD-encapsulated forms of the extracts were prepared in a 3:1 (w:w) proportion through co-precipitation and freeze-drying procedures. A physical mixture was also prepared and used for comparison. The extracts were abbreviated as follows: *Rhodiola heterodonta* L. (RH), *Inula helenium* L. (IH), and *Ginkgo biloba* (GB). Antimicrobial activity was carried out by the agar diffusion scratch assay. Microbial cultures (*Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Candida albicans*) were collected by the Institute of Microbiology of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The microbial cultures were washed from agar and diluted by sterile 0.9% isotonic NaCl until the number of cells reached 10^7 KOE/ml (according to McFarland). Crude and encapsulated extracts were dissolved at 100 mg/mL by distilled water [2]. The experiment was carried out according to with minor modifications. Briefly, for bacteria, commercial nutritional agar (Himedia, India) and for *C. albicans*, commercial Sabouraud agar (Himedia, India) were used. Extract samples were added at 100 μ l, petri dishes kept at fridge 3-4 hours, then incubated at 37°C 20-24 hours for bacteria and 30°C 24-36 hours for *C. albicans*. The experiment was carried out in triplicate.

Cyclodextrins possess significant antimicrobial properties, which contribute to the inhibition of a wide range of microorganisms. Specifically, antimicrobial activity was observed primarily in the pH-adjusted and GB (*Ginkgo biloba*) capsules. Encapsulation of *Candida albicans* and *Staphylococcus* species in a 3:1 ratio within bactericidal capsules demonstrated effective antimicrobial effects. Table 1 provides the pH values, GB content, and results of cyclodextrin-encapsulated extracts, highlighting their antimicrobial activities.

Results: The antagonistic activity of the extracts was studied against five typical cultures of pathogenic and opportunistic microorganisms. The *Rhodiola heterodonta* (RH) extract demonstrated antagonistic activity against most pathogens, except *S. aureus*, including *E. coli* (13 mm), *P. aeruginosa* (22 mm), *B. subtilis* (19 mm), and *C. albicans* (11 mm). The encapsulated form of RH extract with β -cyclodextrin (RH β CD) in a 3:1 ratio showed high antagonistic activity against all tested pathogens: *C. albicans* (24 mm), *S. aureus* (26 mm), *B. subtilis* (22 mm), and *P. aeruginosa* (21 mm). Encapsulation with γ -cyclodextrin (RH γ CD) demonstrated antagonistic activity against *E. coli* (18 mm), *C. albicans* (25 mm), *S. aureus* (24 mm), *B. subtilis* (22 mm), and *P. aeruginosa* (21 mm). The selective activity of *Ginkgo biloba* (GB) extract was also noted, showing maximum activity against *C. albicans* (22 mm), *S. aureus* (18 mm), and *P. aeruginosa* (23 mm). *Inula helenium* (IH) extract showed activity primarily against *C. albicans* (18 mm). Detailed results are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Determination of antimicrobial activity of γ -CD and 2-hp- β -CD encapsulated forms of extracts (b – bactericidal effect)

Test culture	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	<i>Candida albicans</i>	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>
Samples	Zone, mm				
IH/2-hp- β -CD)	-	17 (b)	-	-	-
IH γ CD	-	12 (b)	12 (b)	-	-
IH	-	18 (b)	-	-	-
γ CD	-	-	20 (b)	-	-
β CD	12 (b)	-	-	-	-
GB	-	22 (b)	18	18	10
GB β CD	-	21 (b)	16	18	
GB γ CD	-	-	14	-	-
RH β CD	20 (b)	26 (b)	24 (b)	22 (b)	21
RH	13 (b)	11 (b)	-	19 (b)	22
RH γ CD	18 (b)	25 (b)	-	23(b)	24

Discussion: Medicinal plants continue to be an important source of natural compounds with strong antibacterial effects. The application of cyclodextrins helps overcome the limitations imposed by the low bioavailability of plant secondary metabolites. Recent studies have demonstrated improved bioavailability of *Ginkgo biloba* (GB) extract in the presence of γ -CD, showing 4-, 6.1-, and 10.4-fold enhancements in the plasma levels of quercetin, kaempferol, and isorhamnetin, respectively, when administered as GB/ γ -CD compared to GB alone [6]. *Inula helenium* (IH) is primarily known as an anti-inflammatory agent, although its antimicrobial activity has also been reported, with higher ethanol concentrations during extraction enhancing its inhibitory effects [7]. *Rhodiola heterodonta* (RH), an endemic plant of Uzbekistan, is of significant interest as an adaptogenic remedy. In our study, RH, GB, and IH crude extracts exhibited significant antimicrobial activity, but encapsulation with cyclodextrins reduced the inhibition zones for IH while increasing them for RH and GB. These results highlight the importance of cyclodextrin type, encapsulation methods, and proportion ratios, which can significantly influence

antimicrobial efficacy. Further research is required to identify the optimal proportions of encapsulated substances, the most suitable types of cyclodextrins, and the best encapsulation procedures.

Conclusion. The obtained results indicate that PC, IH, and GB exhibit inhibitory effects against *S. aureus*. IH and GB also demonstrated activity against *C. albicans*. RH was found to be effective against *E. coli*, *P. aeruginosa*, *B. subtilis*, and *C. albicans*. In the presence of cyclodextrins, the inhibitory activity of PC, IH, and GB varied.

REFERENCES

1. Wüpper S, Fischer A, Lüersen K, Lucius R, Okamoto H, Ishida Y, Terao K, Rimbach G. High Dietary Kuding Tea Extract Supplementation Induces Hepatic Xenobiotic-Metabolizing Enzymes-A 6-Week Feeding Study in Mice. *Nutrients*. 2019 Dec 22;12(1):40. doi: 10.3390/nu12010040. PMID: 31877869; PMCID: PMC7019617.
2. Miyoshi N., Wakao Y., Tomono S., Tatemichi M., Yano T., Ohshima H. The enhancement of the oral bioavailability of γ -tocotrienol in mice by γ -cyclodextrin inclusion. *J. Nutr. Biochem.* 2011;22:1121–1126. doi: 10.1016/j.jnutbio.2010.09.011.
3. Rimbach G, Fischer A, Schloesser A, Jerz G, Ikuta N, Ishida Y, Matsuzawa R, Matsugo S, Huebbe P, Terao K. Anti-Inflammatory Properties of Brazilian Green Propolis Encapsulated in a γ -Cyclodextrin Complex in Mice Fed a Western-Type Diet. *Int J Mol Sci.* 2017 May 26;18(6):1140. doi: 10.3390/ijms18061141. PMID: 28587122; PMCID: PMC5485965.
4. Escobar-Avello, D., Avendaño-Godoy, J., Santos, J., Lozano-Castellón, J., Mardones, C., von Baer, D., Luengo, J., Lamuela-Raventós, R.M., Vallverdú-Queralt, A., & Gómez-Gaete, C. (2021). Encapsulation of Phenolic Compounds from a Grape Cane Pilot-Plant Extract in Hydroxypropyl Beta-Cyclodextrin and Maltodextrin by Spray Drying. *Antioxidants*, 10.
5. Hsu CM, Yu SC, Tsai FJ, Tsai Y. Enhancement of rhubarb extract solubility and bioactivity by 2-hydroxypropyl- β -cyclodextrin. *Carbohydr Polym.* 2013 Nov 6;98(2):1422-9. doi: 10.1016/j.carbpol.2013.07.029. Epub 2013 Jul 19. PMID: 24053823.
6. M, Tominaga E, Kito K, et al. Bioavailability of Flavonoids in Ginkgo biloba Extract- γ -Cyclodextrin Complex. *Natural Product Communications.* 2023;18(5). doi:10.1177/1934578X231170221
7. Diguta, Camelia & Cornea, Calina Petruta & Ioniță, L. & Brîndușe, E. & Farcaș, N. & Bobit, D. & (Radoi) Matei, Florentina. (2014). Studies on antimicrobial activity of *Inula helenium* L Romanian cultivar. *Romanian Biotechnological Letters.* 19. 9699-9704.